

Application of Vocational Development Theory in Rebranding Choice of Careers among Nigerian Secondary School Students

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Abstracts:- This paper examined Application of theory of Anne Roe of vocational development in rebranding secondary school students' choice of career in Nigerian education system. Being one of the first model to show the link between childhood events, it has received a lot of attention when it comes to showing psychological needs with career choices. The paper looked into the basics of the vocational development theory by discussing how individuals are integrated entities whose categorization should be based on both his conscious and unconscious need patterns. Relevant literatures reviewed point to the fact the theory's applicability is very vital in helping individuals to choose careers and progress in them. The paper further conversed on how the theory classified parenting rearing practices into being protective and preventive, avoidant and/or accepting and how these are consequent upon career orientation. Moreover, the paper discourse also centered on how the main postulations of the theory could be applied to rebrand secondary school education in Nigeria for example by how the counselor should enable parent gain awareness on the implication of not meeting the psychological and physical needs of the child as they may end up lacking value; and also, how the counsellor should educate parents and clients in understanding why people have different interest to a particular occupation. Finally, the paper revealed that proper application of the vocational development theory would significantly influence students to developed self-concept, self-esteem, and interest to the world work. It therefore recommended that parents should guide the choice of career of their children rather than determine what it is to be and that there should be consultation between parent and the child with the counsellor in order to make meaningful choices in careers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Choice of career is an intricate and vital part of the life of secondary school students in Nigerian educational system as, to a great extent, it determines their future endeavor/work life. In this regard, sometimes parents having experience in life would go a long way to influence careers for their children;

likewise, the economic situation in the country also gives little or no room for such students to adequately make career choices of their liking. These and other factors undeniably affect how some students end up in careers not of their liking and which, at the end, could spell doom for such individuals. Thus, the present phenomenon occurring in Nigerian secondary education with regards students' career choice could largely be attributed to child rearing patterns.

Thus, such child rearing practices tend to make the children dependent upon their parents' choices which could make them more emotional and having poor social relations in their career choices. Thus, Mwaa (2016) and Okeke (2003) aptly points children choice of careers are usually influenced by the parents' careers. Thus, Saleem, Hanan, Saleem, Rao, and Shad (2015) maintain that in selecting careers for children, the thing that plays important role is the parents' occupation. This was, mostly, because such parenting tends to be over protective, over demanding or altogether avoidant.

Therefore, application of the theory of vocational development is necessary in order to rebrand career choice in Nigerian secondary education. Moreover, it is very necessary to provide career guidance services during individual developmental period. Thus, Tiro, Afdal, & Yusuf (2021) observed that, starting from some reasonable years, children could be counseled in order to understand their thinking pattern on choice of career, as this will help in fashioning tracks that could ease their choices. Moreover, the career guidance should be continued even after the individual enters the world of work with the aim of assisting the individual to conveniently adjust to such life so that they could prosper meaningfully.

As explained by Nwawube (2021) that any supposition or a system of ideas intended to explain something, especially one based on general principles independent of the thing to be explained is regarded as a theory. Thus, a theory is a set of principles on which the practice of an activity is based. As applied in career development, the one thing that gives direction to the strategies and techniques that a counselor could utilize in dealing with his clients are theories. They

provide direction on how to attach interest, actions, values, aspirations, and personality of individuals to the type of information about prospective work environments.

The vocational or career development theory studies ways toward improving vocational guidance, professional growth of individuals, and on how to attain overall job satisfaction. In determining individual's core values, strengths, weaknesses and desired intents, an important step is in understanding career development.

Occupation or work undertaken by an individual in his or her lifetime is what can be termed as career. It is also a series of jobs that a person has in a specific field of work, usually requiring more responsibilities as time passes (Okonkwo, 2021). As observed, career choice affects every aspect of a student's life; in this way, one's potential success could be determined by a successful career choice in the same way that one's chance of success could be affected by a bad career choice (Idowu, Ifedayo, & Idowu, 2020). A vital decision that everyone has to make at some stage in their lives is in choice of careers. With regards to students, such decision impacts their course of study in higher learning institutions since it informs them about the choice they made from the variety of subjects in secondary school. Consequently, it has been observed by Camarero-Figuerola, Dueñas, & Renta-Davids (2020) that obtaining appropriate career and educational information from parents, teachers, and relatives has been valued by most students (especially the seniors) because they understood the significance of doing that.

Akinade (2004) opined that Roe (1957) posited that needs determine the nature of interests of individuals, including vocational interests. Therefore, an occupation is a primary source of need satisfaction. He also noted that she viewed an individual as an integrated, organized whole whose categorization or classification, as the case may be should be based on his conscious or unconscious need patterns. Furthermore, he pointed out that she further proposed that every person have a propensity to expend or dispel his strengths in some certain ways. This constitutes the ways individuals change to satisfy their needs throughout their lifetime thus, adapted Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs.

II. RELATED LITERATURE

Most times, over demanding parent forces their children to choose career based on their wishes which may lead the child to choose career against his interest, consequently there will be no career satisfaction throughout the child's life. Sometimes, such parents, without considering the child's disposition, capabilities and interests, asked their children to study a particular course like Medicine, Pharmacy, Law, Engineering etc. They may even infer that they will only pay the child's school's fee if he/she followed their wishes, which is not appropriated and may result to child's poor academic achievement and unsatisfactory career decision. Thus, Salami

(2006) pointed out that in Nigeria, advice from parents and teachers, ignorance, inexperience or because of stigma attached to certain jobs are what mostly pushed many people, especially the young, in making the wrong career choices and this is because sufficient technical guidance and career advice is lacking in our educational system.

In support of the applicability of the vocational development theory in rebranding career choice in Nigerian secondary education, Savickas (2012) observed that the mechanism that offers and empowers inspiration and proficiently sustained strategies to the problem of youth career development is career decision-making.

Interestingly, the study by Idowu, Ifedayo & Idowu (2020) revealed that formal education of parents significantly influences students' choice of career, and also that students' choice of career is to an extent affected by parents' nature of job. Furthermore, the findings also show that students' choice of career was not affected by parents' socio-economic status. Consequent upon the findings, the study recommends that effective career counseling be given to help parents appropriately direct their children in their choices of careers.

III. ROE'S CATEGORIZATION OF CHILD REARING PRACTICES AND CAREER ORIENTATION

Roe categorized child rearing practices into three major categories and their subsequent career orientation into protective and demanding, rejecting and neglecting, and casual and loving. Moreover, Martina (2021) noted that the three child rearing practices were further divided into two categories each.

➤ *Protective and Demanding.*

Parents that are protective of their children usually emphasized on indulgence and the child is always shielded from taking part in activities for fear that the child's inefficiency would be seen or for fear that he could get hurt. But, invariably, this only leads to the child being dependent and lacking in ingenuity, so also lacking in authenticity; sometimes children raised under such circumstances hardly actualize themselves because they are raised under a lot of rules and regulations.

On the contrary, parents that are demanding always set goals that have to be achieved before the child could be shown care and love i.e. love and care are always contingent upon toeing the line and attainment. Thus, such individuals learned that their needs will happen only when they performed in a required way.

Consequently, children raised in both protective and demanding situations, engage in professions in which they want and hang on acceptance and recognition from other people. Thus, they mostly engage in job-related areas that are

people oriented, for example in the sports, drama, music and theater arts etc. and for some others they engage in being clergymen/women (get involved in religious activities), counselors, teachers, social (help) workers and the likes.

➤ *Rejecting and Neglecting.*

This type of rearing condition of the child happens where the parents are insensitive to the child's need to be accepted and noticed; the parents will somehow be emotionally or physically unattached to the needs of the child and thus show tendency to show him much recognition or none at all whatsoever.

Usually, as a way of finding gratification, such children grow up and engage in work-related jobs that mostly have to do with non-persons or things because they hardly enjoy relating with people believing deep down in them that they have nothing to offer them in terms of compassion and solace. Such children raised under this type parenting style engage in professions that ensure as little as possible contact with other people and thus went into jobs such as nature explorations, marine, hydro and geo sciences, computing sciences and the likes.

➤ *Casual and Loving.*

Children that are raised under the casual acceptance type of parenting style get to understand that they are prepared to 'get on well'. In this regard, it has been noted that such children grew up being close minded due that no adequate obligation has been expended to appropriate nurture (Okeke, 2003). Though such children both gravitate toward people and also obviate from them, with little motivation they could easily adjust and accustom towards them.

On the other hand, children raised under the loving acceptance parenting style received judicious level of fulfillment for all needs and thus is definitely the reason that makes the difference between the two types. Conversely, children reared in such situation grow to seek satisfaction of their wants in all its implications. Consequently, such individual blend in well with both 'people-oriented' and 'things-oriented' occupations and work settings.

Furthermore, as observed by Blanton (2015) & Martina (2021) that the vocational development theory categorizes vocations based on the level of the job skill into eight groups of service; entertainment, outdoor, general culture, technology, organization, arts, science, and business.

However, based on how much proficiency is requisite for the profession, the theory further promoted independent responsibility, less independence, moderate responsibility, training required, special training and follow basic instructions as levels of the above categories. Then based on the type and kind of parenting style an individual receives, he is then classified into any of eight categories and six levels.

IV. APPLICATION OF THE VOCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT THEORY IN REBRANDING CHOICE OF CAREER IN NIGERIAN SECONDARY EDUCATION

The theory of vocational development can be applied to rebrand choice of career in Nigerian secondary education through organizing seminars for parent and youth especially. Creating awareness in the mosques, churches or anywhere that counselling could make an impact by having a professionally trained counsellor to explain how parents and family have important roles that could make or mar in charting career course of their children. The counselor could also educate on the implication of parenting styles on their children's future career choice. These could be done through the followings:

Since, being over protective and too demanding is related to parents that are considered as emotionally concentrated, the counselor should let parents understand the kind of children that could be raised by such parenting; about how such children always crave for acceptance, regard, and respect from others to the extent that they rely on others to value them and in fact be contingent on others for whatever they do.

Furthermore, the counselor should enlighten parents on the implication of avoiding or rejecting their children as they may end up not holding themselves in high esteem. This is because, usually for such children, their basic needs were ignored by their parents and such may grow up weighted with the feeling of rejection. Accordingly, as way for gaining recognition, such children may opt for non-person or things oriented careers.

Similarly, for accepting parents, the counselor should encourage them and others too to be accepting and supportive of their children as this will go long way in physically and psychologically empowering their children to grow up having the necessary confidence and courage to be independent and engage in and balance careers that are both personal- and non-personal. In this regard, the counselor should work with the parents to ensure that they understand and relentlessly make provisions for their children's needs. In essence, guidance and counseling professionals should make efforts in assisting children gain awareness on how they can make their choices in respective careers of interest.

Counsellors could help with identifying information useful in creating new strategies in choosing career according to individuals' personality by specifically guiding you in using tools and tests that could effectively help in choosing the right career. This empowers the person to orient towards careers that will enable him if he will interact more with others, or things or just be more into facts and figures. This is because empirical researches supported Roe's theory in validating the links between personality factors and vocational preferences. This empirical grounding provides credibility to her theory

and enhances its applicability in such situations as Nigerian education.

It can assist with understanding what practices promote specific behaviors or habits by helping to determine specific behaviors and what motivates students to be successful in career choice. Thus, counsellors should help in recognizing that individual differences in personality traits and interests play a crucial role in vocational choice and considering personality factors this would undoubtedly provide a more comprehensive understanding of career development.

Counsellor should let people understand that environmental factors, such as socioeconomic status, educational opportunities, and cultural norms, can significantly influence an individual's career choices and opportunities. This recognition emphasizes the importance of societal, contextual, and structural factors in career development.

V. SUMMARY

The vocational theory emphasized that in choosing careers, individuals may be influenced by prior interaction they had their parents. The theory further maintains that that type and kind of interaction made individuals pursue person- or non-person-oriented careers. Careers that enable high interaction with other people are regarded as person-oriented and on the other hand careers that are more independent are classified as non-person-oriented. Based on interaction individuals had with their parents, they could be classified into eight categories of six levels. Counselling helps in bridging the gap in understanding how parents influence career choices of their children from the kind of parenting they give them and what kind of choice the children actually have.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the above discussions, the following were some of the suggestions made:

- Career conferences should be periodically organized for children and parents alike; where the focused should be on how best to plan and choose careers.
- Awareness campaigns should be mounted in which emphasis should be on patterns of child-rearing practice and its implications.
- Counseling services should educate parents on how best to help their children in making decisions about their career choices rather than choosing careers for their children as this may not be in the best interest of all.
- Government should provide professionally trained counsellors particularly in Nigerian secondary schools, in order to help students in choosing careers that suite their personalities.

- There should be consultation between parent and the child with the counsellor in order to make meaningful choices in careers.

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